

On the Characterization of Membranes

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Characterization of membranes on the basis of conductance and permeability data has been discussed. Membrane constant and equivalent pore radius of a Pyrex-G₄ membrane equilibrated with sodium chloride, potassium chloride, barium chloride and aluminium chloride solutions have been estimated. These membrane parameters and zeta-potentials have also been determined in the case of Zeokarb-225 (H⁺ form) membrane using methanol-water mixtures as permeants. Characterization of an aluminium-oxide membrane has also been accomplished from permeation data obtained at different temperatures.

NON-equilibrium thermodynamic treatment¹⁻⁴ is often used for the description of membrane transport phenomena occurring under the simultaneous action of gradients of hydrodynamic pressure and electrical field. This treatment is independent of structural details of the membrane and characterises the system in terms of a set of experimentally accessible phenomenological coefficients. For a proper understanding and prediction of a membrane permeation characteristics, however, an insight into the structural details, e.g., effective cross-sectional area, equivalent pore radius and the electrical character of the membrane permeant interface are needed.

In the present communication, we report studies on hydrodynamic and electroosmotic permeabilities of water and aqueous electrolyte solutions through a pyrex membrane. Similar measurements with (i) zeokarb-225 (H⁺ form), ion-exchange membranes, using methanol and methanol-water mixtures as permeants and (ii) an aluminiumoxide membrane using methanol as permeant at different temperatures, have also been carried out. Electrical conductivities of the equilibrated membranes have also been measured. The data have been used to ascertain membrane permeation characteristics.

Experimental

Zeokarb-225 (Na⁺ form), obtained from Permutit Company London, was used for the preparation of the ion-exchange membranes. It had an exchange capacity of 4.8 meq/gm dry resin and moisture content equal to 50% by weight.

It was converted into H⁺ form by equilibrating it with 1 molar HCl for over 24 hours. The particles were then repeatedly washed with distilled water in

order to remove the excess acid present. Ion-exchange membranes was then prepared by the mechanical compression as described earlier^{1,2,5}. Pyrex-G₄ sinter was also used as a membrane. It was cleaned in the usual manner⁶. Aluminium oxide membrane was prepared by taking a small amount of basic active aluminium oxide (B.D.H.) along with a small amount of an adhesive, Araldite, and keeping it compressed mechanically in the middle of a glass tube for over 24 hours. The plug formed was 1.6 cm long and 1.2 cm in diameter. Sodium chloride, potassium chloride, barium chloride, aluminium chloride and methanol (AR, BDH) was used without further purification. Distilled water was double distilled with alkaline KMnO₄. Specific conductivity of the water used was of the order of 1⁻⁶ mhos-cm⁻¹.

Hydrodynamic and electroosmotic permeabilities were measured by using the experimental procedure described in our earlier publications^{1,2,5}. An electronically operated power supply was used for the application of electrical potential difference. The rate of permeation was estimated by noting the movement of the permeant in a horizontally placed graduated capillary tube of known cross-sectional area. Conductance of the membrane and specific conductivity of the permeant were measured by means of a conductivity bridge at 50 cycles/sec. Viscosities of the methanol-water mixtures were measured with a modified Tuonfuoss viscometer⁷. The measurements were carried out in an air-thermostat maintained at 303 ± 3.5 K, in the case of pyrex and zeokarb-225 membranes and at 298, 303, 308, 313 ± 0.5 K, in the case of aluminium oxide membrane.

Results and Discussion

The rate of permeation through a membrane under the action of hydrostatic pressure and/or electrical

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gradient depends on the effective cross-sectional area, A , and the thickness of the membrane, l . An unambiguous determination of either of these quantities is difficult due to complex geometry of the openings within the membrane. It is, however, possible to determine A/l , the membrane constant, in terms of which permeation behaviour of any membrane can be quantitatively expressed.

Let us consider a membrane having n pores of equivalent radius ' r ' and effective length, l . The effective cross-sectional area, A , of this membrane through which permeation occurs is $n\pi r^2$. The electrical conductance of the membrane equilibrated with a permeant having specific conductivity, k , is

given by⁸

$$K = \frac{n \pi r^2 k}{l} = \frac{A}{l} k \quad \dots (1)$$

so that, the membrane constant ; $\frac{A}{l} = \frac{K}{k} \quad \dots (2)$

The membrane conductance can thus easily be used for the determination of membrane constant. This constant is characteristic of the membrane and is independent of the nature of the permeating liquid, so long as interaction between the permeant and the membrane matrix is not strong enough to alter its equivalent pore radius. Membrane constant values obtained from conductance data are given in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 for different membrane permeant systems.

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE CHARACTERISTICS FOR PYREX/ELECTROLYTE SYSTEM : AT 303 ± 0.5 K.

Electrolyte/ Concentration (Moles litre ⁻¹)	$L_{11} \times 10^5$ (cm ² sec ⁻¹ dyne ⁻¹ K)	$L_{12} \times 10^5$ (cm ² sec ⁻¹ volt ⁻¹ K)	$K \times 10^6$ (Mhos)	$k \times 10^5$ (Mhos- cm ⁻¹)	$\frac{A}{l} \times 10^1$ (cm.)	$r \times 10^4$ (cm.)
NaCl						
0.0000	9.88	4.48	1.50	1.19	1.25	4.07
0.0001	9.39	5.24	2.60	2.55	1.02	4.41
0.0005	9.64	7.24	7.50	6.52	1.15	4.21
0.0010	9.51	8.18	12.00	11.22	1.07	4.33
KCl						
0.0000	8.94	4.82	1.30	1.19	1.09	4.16
0.0001	9.03	5.58	2.50	2.13	1.12	4.03
0.0005	9.70	6.33	8.00	6.82	1.17	4.18
0.0010	9.27	6.61	15.00	—	—	—
BaCl₂						
0.0000	13.15	3.82	1.50	1.08	1.39	4.47
0.0001	13.33	4.48	3.50	2.43	1.44	4.42
0.0005	13.18	5.21	14.00	10.08	1.39	4.48
0.0010	13.09	6.09	27.00	19.60	1.38	4.48
AlCl₃						
0.0000	11.76	4.51	1.25	1.01	1.24	4.48
0.0001	11.54	-4.30	2.50	2.10	1.19	4.53
0.0005	11.51	-6.09	8.00	6.67	1.20	4.50
0.0010	11.85	-8.76	16.00	12.50	1.28	4.42

Note : L_{12}/T : Positive sign indicates electroosmotic flow from positive towards negative electrode and negative sign indicates its reverse.

TABLE 2—MEMBRANE CHARACTERISTICS FOR ZEOKARB-225 (H⁺ FORM)/METHANOL-WATER SYSTEM ASCERTAINED FROM PERMEABILITY AND CONDUCTANCE DATA, AT 303 ± 0.5 K.

Mole fraction of water	$L_{11} \times 10^4$ (cm ⁵ sec ⁻¹ dyne ⁻¹ K)	$L_{12} \times 10^4$ (cm ⁵ sec ⁻¹ volt ⁻¹ K)	$K \times 10^7$ (mhos)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Poise)	$k \times 10^6$ (mhos cm ⁻¹)	ϵ	$\frac{A}{l} \times 10^1$ (cm)	$r \times 10^4$ (cm)	$\zeta \times 10^3$ (Volts)
0.1	3.18	5.33	2.85	5.67	2.280	35.7	1.25	6.14	3.19
0.2	2.70	4.73	3.00	6.67	2.375	38.0	1.26	6.13	2.45
0.3	2.24	4.18	3.30	7.44	2.451	40.5	1.35	5.72	2.13
0.4	1.84	2.91	3.65	8.74	2.637	43.5	1.38	5.43	1.57
0.5	1.76	2.85	3.80	9.84	2.801	47.3	1.36	5.67	1.62

TABLE 3—PHENOMENOLOGICAL-COEFFICIENTS, MEMBRANE CONSTANT, l_{11} AND l_{12} VALUES FOR DIFFERENT ZEOKARB-225 (H⁺ FORM)/METHANOL SYSTEM : T = 303 ± 0.5 K.

Membranes	$L_{11} \times 10^4$ (cm ⁵ sec ⁻¹ dyne ⁻¹ K)	$L_{12} \times 10^4$ (cm ⁵ sec ⁻¹ volt ⁻¹ K)	$K \times 10^7$ (mhos)	$k \times 10^6$ (mhos cm ⁻¹)	$\frac{A}{l} \times 10^1$ (cm)	$r \times 10^4$ (cm)	$l_{11} \times 10^3$ (cm ⁴ dyne ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ K)	$l_{12} \times 10^3$ (cm ⁵ sec ⁻¹ volt ⁻¹ K)
I	5.21	1.78	1.97	2.22	0.89	9.19	5.92	2.00
II	7.00	2.18	2.46		1.11	9.53	6.32	1.97
III	8.88	2.74	2.98		1.34	9.75	6.62	2.03

TABLE 4—PHENOMENOLOGICAL COEFFICIENTS, MEMBRANE CONSTANT AND MEMBRANE TRANSPORT COEFFICIENTS FOR ALUMINIUM OXIDE-METHANOL SYSTEM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES.

T (K)	$L_{11} \times 10^3$ (cm ⁵ dyne ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ K)	$L_{12} \times 10^3$ (cm ⁵ sec ⁻¹ volt ⁻¹ K)	$K \times 10^5$ (mhos)	$k \times 10^6$ (mhos cm ⁻¹)	$\frac{A}{l}$ (cm)	$r \times 10^4$ (cm)	$l_{11} \times 10^3$ (cm ⁴ dyne ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ K)	$l_{12} \times 10^3$ (cm ⁵ sec ⁻¹ volt ⁻¹ K)
298	1.007	4.470	0.150	6.766	0.22	8.18	4.54	2.02
303	1.130	5.907	0.165	7.381	0.22	8.26	5.05	2.64
308	1.269	7.548	0.180	7.791	0.23	8.28	5.49	3.27
313	1.408	8.919	0.190	8.200	0.23	8.41	6.08	3.85

A/l values in the case of pyrex membrane are reasonably constant. In the case of aluminium oxide membrane, the membrane constant is seen to be unaffected by temperature variation within the range of the present investigation. But, in the case of ion-exchange membrane, zeokarb-225, the membrane constant no longer remains constant. The ion-exchange materials exhibit varied swelling when composition of the permeating liquid is varied. The observed increase in A/l is largely due to diminished swelling of the ion-exchanger in water rich mixtures.

Once the membrane constant is known it is possible to derive 'r' from hydrodynamic permeability

data, since, according to Poisseuille's equation :

$$\left(\frac{J_v}{\Delta P}\right)_{\Delta\phi=0} = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l} = \frac{A}{l} \frac{r^2}{8\eta}$$

$$\text{or, } r = \left(\frac{8\eta(J_v/\Delta P)_{\Delta\phi=0}}{A/l}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (3)$$

where, η is the viscosity of the permeant ; J_v , the volume flux ; ΔP , the pressure difference and $\Delta\phi$, the electrical potential difference.

The derived value of r will of course be unambiguous, only, when the dimension of the permeant molecules is

much smaller than the openings within the membrane. The values of 'r' obtained by using the above equation are given in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4, for pyrex, zeokarb-225 and aluminium oxide membranes.

The electrical character of a membrane permeant interface can be expressed in terms of zeta-potential, when $r \gg$ double layer thickness⁹. A knowledge of the membrane constant is also helpful in the estimation of zeta-potential, ξ , from electro-osmotic permeability data. According to the double layer picture electro-osmotic permeability is given by¹⁰

$$\left(\frac{J_v}{\Delta\phi}\right)_{\Delta P=0} = \frac{n\epsilon r^2 \xi}{4\eta l}$$

or, $\xi = \frac{4\pi\eta(J_v/\Delta\phi)_{\Delta P=0}}{\epsilon(A/l)} \dots (4)$

where, ϵ is the dielectric constant of the permeant. $(J_v/\Delta\phi)_{\Delta P=0}$ has been found to be independent of $\Delta\phi$, upto 100 volts, in the case of electrolyte solutions. ξ , thus, remains unaltered when $\Delta\phi$ is varied within the range of investigation. ξ values obtained using equation (4) are given in Table 2, in the case of Zeokarb-225 membrane.

Transport phenomena through membranes under the simultaneous action of ΔP and $\Delta\phi$, on the basis of non-equilibrium thermodynamic theory, are given by^{11,12}

$$J_v = L_{11}\left(\frac{\Delta P}{T}\right) + L_{12}\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{T}\right) \dots (5)$$

$$I = L_{21}\left(\frac{\Delta P}{T}\right) + L_{22}\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{T}\right) \dots (6)$$

L_{ij} (i,j=1,2) are phenomenological coefficients. Onsager's reciprocity relationship established firmly¹³⁻¹⁵ on the basis of experimental data on electrokinetic phenomena requires that $L_{12}=L_{21}$. It is obvious that

$$\left(\frac{J_v}{\Delta P}\right)_{\Delta\phi=0} = \frac{L_{11}}{T}; \left(\frac{J_v}{\Delta\phi}\right)_{\Delta P=0} = \frac{L_{12}}{T}; \text{ and } \left(\frac{I}{\Delta\phi}\right)_{\Delta P=0} = \frac{L_{22}}{T} = K.$$

L_{11} and L_{12} values estimated from flux data, and the membrane conductance, $K=L_{22}/T$, from conductance data are, also included in Tables 1,2,3, and 4 for the pyrex, zeokarb-225 and alumina membranes.

It has been argued¹⁶ that equation (5) may advantageously be written as

$$J_v = \frac{A}{l} L_{11}\left(\frac{\Delta P}{T}\right) + \frac{A}{l} L_{12}\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{T}\right) \dots (7)$$

The phenomenological coefficients L_{11} and L_{12} have been estimated from hydrodynamic and electroosmotic permeability data for three different zeokarb-225, ion-exchange membranes, are included in Table 3 and for alumina membrane at different temperatures are included in table 4, along with membrane constant values. The values of the membrane transport coefficients l_{11} and l_{12} , are also given in Tables 3 and 4 for different zeokarb-225 membranes and alumina membrane at different temperatures. From Tables 3 and 4, it is seen that L_{11} and L_{12} are different for different membranes but l_{11} and l_{12} values are, however, fairly constant at a given temperature and unique for the membrane permeant system.

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of the membrane transport coefficient, l_{11} .

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of the membrane transport coefficient, l_{12} .

The plots given in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, show that temperature dependence of these coefficients may be expressed as

$$l_{11} = \alpha_1 + \beta_1 T \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{and } l_{12} = \alpha_2 + \beta_2 T \quad \dots (9)$$

where; α_1 , α_2 , β_1 and β_2 are constants and T is temperature in K. From the plots of l_{11} vs. T, and l_{12} vs. T.,

$$\alpha_1 = -2.53 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^4 \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ K.},$$

$$\beta_1 = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^4 \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1},$$

$$\alpha_2 = -3.47 \times 10^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1} \text{ K.},$$

$$\text{and } \beta_2 = 1.232 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1}.$$

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